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The Effect of the Phenomenon of Phubbing on the Organizational Behavior of Administrators Working in Vocational Education Schools in The Light of the Variables of Appreciation and Provision of Attention to Employees

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Abstract

The aim of this research is to identify the effect of the phenomenon of Phubbing on the organizational behavior of administrators working in vocational schools in the light of the variables of appreciation and Provision of Attention to Employees. The research community consisted of (45) administrators, who were selected in a stratified random manner. The descriptive survey method was used in the current research. To achieve the objectives of the research, a questionnaire was developed, and its validity and reliability were confirmed. The results showed that the effect of the phenomenon of Phubbing on the organizational behavior of administrators working in vocational education schools in the light of the variables of appreciation and concern for workers was medium. The results of the research also showed that there were statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) according to the gender variable in favor of the male category. And there were no statistically significant differences according to the educational qualification variable, and there were no statistically significant differences according to the years of experience variable. In light of these results, the research recommended that the administrations of vocational education schools attach great importance to organizational behavior And work on treating it and alleviating the obstacles it faces and trying to tackle the phenomenon of Phubbing, So that it works to stimulate conducting studies and research from time to time to find out the effects of this phenomenon on organizational behavior in various circumstances and organizational variables in the educational administrative environment.

Keywords: Phubbing, Organizational Behavior, Vocational Education Schools

1. Introduction

Organizational behavior is a comprehensive attempt to understand the practices of employees in the organization, whether they are individuals or small groups. The organizational behavior also expresses the organization's interaction with its external environment, such as political, economic, social, cultural and civil influences and factors. And with the behavior of its employees and the feelings, attitudes, attitudes, motives, expectations, efforts and capabilities they hold, Organizational behavior aims to improve performance, administrative effectiveness and

job satisfaction among employees. In order to achieve the common and desired goals of the employee as an individual and for the organization in which he works, in order to achieve the goals of society as a whole, the organizational behavior has crystallized within the framework of the development of contemporary administrative thought, especially in the field of organizational thinking. It has become the most influential factor in achieving administrative goals, because of its great role in shaping and formulating the behavior of individuals, as well as being a function of the level of interaction between the individual and his environment.

Therefore, recognizing the nature of the prevailing organizational behavior in any organization in its various dimensions is necessary and important, it seeks to adopt policies and procedures that enhance the positive aspects and correct the negative aspects, and the advancement of the mental health of its employees, their morale, and their moral values, which is reflected positively on the efficiency and effectiveness of the process of achieving the organization's goals, and satisfying individual and organizational needs and desires (Al-Saud, 2015).

It is worth noting that the good human relations, which prevail among individuals in the same organization, help to create and create healthy organizational behavior, based on the way managers treat their subordinates, the philosophy of senior management, working conditions, the quality of goals and objectives that the organization seeks to achieve, Where the level of organizational behavior is affected by the change in the general atmosphere that prevails in the internal environment, with all its conditions and variables, With its level of civilization and stability, and the extent of the rule of democratic dimensions in it, which is based on the fundamental idea that the multiplicity of healthy minds is more capable of presenting correct ideas than a single, sound mind (Al-Mutairi, 2016).

From here, the prevailing organizational behavior of individuals works to formulate and shape the characteristics of the organization in all its dimensions, and work to identify the difficulties and obstacles that may stand in the way of the organization's realization of its programs, Which may weaken the organization's ability to create the appropriate climate if the prevailing organizational behavior is negative, this is on the grounds that individuals working in the organizational environment who do not feel their importance at work, and the value of the tasks they perform, And they do not receive the appreciation they deserve, which may weaken their ability to achieve organizational goals successfully, and generate mutual mistrust between them and the management of the organization. This reflects negatively on the nature of the work environment prevailing in the organization, and then the organized values of hatred, envy and jealousy are generated, Conspiracies and intrigues abound, and a state of melancholy organized affection and lack of sincerity in performing tasks and duties prevails, Organizational diseases, feelings of injustice, widespread depression and unwillingness to continue working are prevalent in the workplace, But the organizational behavior may lead to stability and organizational stability and the achievement of the goals and objectives set in the organization's plans if the behavior of the employees and the management of the organization tends to be positive, And in a way that achieves the organization's vision, mission and goals efficiently and effectively so organizations, while living the modern administration with an accelerating pace, work to establish a conscious understanding of the level of organizational behavior, And work on analyzing its elements in order to identify the direct and indirect influences on the actions and motives of individuals in order to treat, improve and develop performance, Increasing productivity in light of satisfying the functional, psychological, social and material needs of the individual (Al-Baher, 2021).

The organizational behavior is a true reflection of the interaction of many factors that appear on the individual in the course of his practices towards his work, whether those factors are related to the individual himself; as the experience gained, Or the academic qualification obtained from a university, college or institute, or its gender, whether male or female, With all its physiological, psychological or sociological characteristics and characteristics (Al-Qaryouti, 2006).

But in light of the spread of the phenomenon of Phubbing, especially among senior management in various organizations, this led to creating gaps in the nature of the prevailing organizational behavior in those organizations, As the manager's distraction with his phone at the expense of his interaction with the workers and the inability to communicate with them effectively may reflect on the psychological feeling of the workers This may take another curve, which is represented in the misjudgment and poor evaluation of the superior effort and

the lack of reward for outstanding work on the one hand, and the poor attention to workers on the other hand, Such a matter may generate a state of organizational animosity between workers and their higher management, Several studies have confirmed the negative impact of the phenomenon of Phubbing, such as the study of James A. Roberts in 2015, The media reported that these researches about ignoring the individual because of his preoccupation with the phone or the so-called “Phubbing phenomenon” found that 22.6% caused them problems in their relationship, And 66.3% said their partners ignored them (Caglare, 2013).

Therefore, in light of this, the phenomenon of Phubbing constitutes an organizational concern in organizations, especially those concerned with learning and education, this is on the basis that this phenomenon may create a state of estrangement between employees and their management and may lead to the emergence of organizational diseases such as work turnover, High levels of absenteeism, poor performance of tasks and duties to the fullest, and lack of efficiency and effectiveness, Weak exploitation of human and material resources and the failure of the organization to achieve its goals, The loss of the educational service recipients’ trust in the organization and its services, and the prevailing organizational climate based on catching mistakes, And the spread of conspiracies as a result of the higher management giving its attention to administrators rather than administrators and to matters without other matters.

2. Research problem

Any administrative or educational organization seeks to achieve the highest levels of efficiency in work and effectiveness in the performance of its employees, so that it is keen on everything that would raise the level of employees, In a manner that ensures a high level of interaction and integration, and active participation in fulfilling the duties and tasks assigned to them, Looking at vocational education schools, the researcher noticed a decrease in the level of organizational behavior among the administrators working in them as a result of the presence of the phenomenon of phubbing in the departments of vocational education schools, Where a large degree of disparity has been established in the level of practices, behaviors and ethical values that must be available to workers to ensure the proper completion of their work, And in a way that ensures the highest levels of interaction and integration in their jobs, so it was important to research the impact of the Phubbing phenomenon that led to the emergence of that problem and related to the level of organizational behavior in the light of the variables of appreciation and concern for workers, Therefore, this study comes as a step towards contributing to the establishment of a solid base for organizational behavior in these institutions. Perhaps what confirms the impact of the phenomenon of Phubbing on organizational behavior that may occur in any organization, the results of the study of; Caglare (2013), Erbas (2014), Sulu (2015), and Chotpitayasunondh, Douglas (2018).

3. Research questions

The research seeks to identify the impact of the phenomenon of Phubbing on the organizational behavior of administrators working in vocational schools in the light of the variables of appreciation and concern for workers, By answering the following questions:

- The first question: What is the effect of the phenomenon of Phubbing on the organizational behavior of administrators working in vocational schools in the light of the variables of appreciation and concern for workers?
- The second question: Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the arithmetic averages of the responses of the study sample members towards the effect of the phenomenon of Phubbing on organizational behavior in vocational education schools due to the variables (gender, years of experience, and educational qualification)?

4. Research aims

This research aims to achieve the following:

- Adding new knowledge in the field of the phenomenon of Phubbing and its impact on organizational behavior in educational organizations.

- Helping those in charge of decision-making and policies in the administrative and educational fields to create an environment for the social system within vocational schools by reducing the spread of the phenomenon of Phubbing in those educational institutions.
- Work to generate a state of harmony in the work of the employees, and their good management of the functional affairs that they carry out, and to ensure that the goals of vocational education schools are achieved efficiently and effectively.

5. Research terms

The search included the following terms:

- **Phubbing:** A term coined as part of the Macquarie Dictionary campaign to describe the habit of ignoring someone in favor of a mobile phone, It is an acronym for 'phone snubbing' or 'ignoring others for using the phone', It is a term used to describe the habit of ignoring the person sitting with you due to the preference for using a mobile phone (Chotpitayasunondh, Douglas, 2018).
- **Organizational Behavior:** It is concerned with studying the behavior of employees in different organizational units, their tendencies, tendencies and performance (Al-Baher, 2021).
- **Vocational education schools:** they are educational institutions concerned with education, training and rehabilitation, the aim of which is to prepare students for the labor market directly (Al-Saud, 2015).

6. Research limits

Research limitations include:

- Human limits: administrators working in vocational education schools.
- Time limits: the second half of the 2021/2022 school year.
- Spatial boundaries: Jordanian vocational education schools.

7. Related previous studies

This part will include a presentation of the previous studies that were reviewed, both Arab and foreign, arranged historically from the most recent to the oldest, as follows:

Garrido (2021) conducted a study represented the practice of phubbing has become an emerging phenomenon of worldwide interest to researchers. The cause is due to the fact that smartphones are ubiquitous and are often used in co-present interactions. This behavior is generally considered inappropriate and is called "phubbing." Phubbing, as described by Chotpitayasunondh is the act of snubbing someone in a social setting by looking at one's phone instead of paying attention to the other person. The aim of this article is to provide an overview of research studies on phubbing through a review of the current literature. To do this, a search was carried out in an international database, finding 84 relevant articles in English that appeared in peer-reviewed journals published between 2012, the year in which the term 'phubbing' appears, and January 2020. The review covers the main fields of research studies on phubbing behaviors. Likewise, the results of the study show the distribution of published articles on phubbing by year that detail the type of study and the methodological approach and, finally, the research journals that have published articles on phubbing. The results of this review are expected to stimulate and guide future research in this field.

Nazir (2019) conducted a study represented by the use of social networking sites and other mobile applications that have been growing intensively. Several researches indicated that it is one of the factors that impact the relationship maintenance between one another. It is highly desirable for all citizens to have a good interpersonal communication to maintain and develop further relationships. Bad communication skills may have harmed the interpersonal relationships. With technology advancing, Smartphone's play an important part in people's lives. It's easy to see people talking, slipping, or even playing on their phones in public places. Certainly, when people are concentrating on the small screens in hands, they won't care about their plights. So the probability of an accident is higher than before. Some countries even set up the "mobile phone sidewalk" to reduce potential hazards. But that is just palliatives. People needed to find a solution that "describe the annoying situation and

further remind people to put their phones down, and get talking to each other again.” In response to this request, a new word “phubbing” was created.

Chotpitayasunondh, Douglas (2018) conducted a study experimentally investigated the social consequences of “phubbing” – the act of snubbing someone in a social setting by concentrating on one’s mobile phone. Participants viewed a three-minute animation in which they imagined themselves as part of a dyadic conversation. Their communication partner either phubbed them extensively, partially, or not at all. Results revealed that increased phubbing significantly and negatively affected perceived communication quality and relationship satisfaction. These effects were mediated by reduced feelings of belongingness and both positive and negative affect. This research underlines the importance of phubbing as a modern social phenomenon to be further investigated.

The study of Massad (2016) aimed to measure the relationship between the level of organizational behavior and job performance among workers in engineering departments. The study population was represented by all employees in the various engineering departments in the ministry, including department managers, department heads, and engineers. The method that was followed in selecting the sample is the stratified random sampling method, where the total sample size was distributed over seven layers representing the employees of the Ministry's Presidency and its branches, What is the tool that was used in collecting the data are the questionnaires, where a questionnaire was designed consisting of three sections, Each section contains a set of questions directed to employees directly to inquire of them about their feelings and opinions about many issues related to themselves, their work, and the organization as a whole. The statistical analysis program (SPSS) was used to analyze the data and show the final results and circulate them to the study population. The study found out the reasons that lead to a sense of dissatisfaction among workers, the most important of which were: The lack of opportunity for renewal and innovation through job performance, and the promotion system in the ministry is not satisfactory, freedom of opinion is not available in the job, The working conditions and the physical environment are not appropriate, the method of supervision and direction by the administration on the workers is not satisfactory, the organizational structure in the ministry is not clear, Job tasks are changing from time to time, slow communication process between the various parties inside and outside the ministry, poor coordination and information exchange between different departments within the ministry, unfair distribution of incentives.

The study of Sulu (2015) came to identify the relationship that organizational behavior causes between two important variables in the business sector, namely, organizational injustice and organizational loyalty, and whether organizational behavior affects health care workers. The descriptive analytical method and questionnaire were used as a tool for the current study, and the researchers tested these relationships in a sample of 383 healthcare professionals (nurses and doctors) from public and private hospitals in Istanbul. The results of the study showed that there was a statistically significant correlation between the dimensions of job behavior and organizational loyalty due to the benefit of the dimensions of job alienation. The results showed that there is a relationship between workers in the health sector for the variable of organizational injustice and organizational loyalty in favor of females in the two variables.

Abu Wassan (2015) conducted a study aimed at knowing the role of organizational behavior in the performance of business organizations and determining the role of organizational behavior in the performance of these organizations. To achieve this goal, three commercial banks were selected as a sample representing the Sudanese banking sector. The student used the questionnaire as a main tool for collecting primary data from a stratified random sample of 220 individuals from the study population, which consists of the upper, middle and lower departments of the selected banks. (190) valid questionnaires were retrieved and analyzed using the SPSS statistical analysis package, and the descriptive analytical method was used for its suitability to the nature of the study. The study proposed a model consisting of some dimensions of organizational behavior, where (attitudes, motivation and motivation, work pressures, administrative leadership, organizational conflict, and organizational culture) were identified as dimensions for measuring organizational behavior. Also, (efficiency, effectiveness, quality of performance and organizational commitment) were used as dimensions to measure the performance of banks, as for the internal environment of the organization (modified variable), the study chose (organizational structure, technology, physical environment, and procedures) as dimensions to be measured.

And Erbas (2014), conducted a study, the aim of this study was to determine the relationship between the levels of organizational behavior and the attitudes and attitudes of students nominated for a physical education teacher, Towards the teaching profession in faculties of physical education, sports faculties and the Department of Education, and determining the relationship between their levels of behavior and attitudes, Whether there are any statistically significant differences between the variables: type and grade. The study group consisted of 695 candidates from teachers who study in the departments of education, physical education and sports. The correlational approach and the correlational research model were used in this study, in order to determine the relationship between two or more variables. The study revealed that the differences between the levels of functional behavior and the attitudes of physical education teacher candidates towards the teaching profession were moderate, the levels of alienation predicted significant levels of attitudes towards the teaching profession due to the grade variable.

Caglarc (2013) conducted a study that aimed to ascertain the relationship between the levels of organizational behavior of students of the College of Education, and their attitudes towards the teaching profession. The research sample consisted of 875 students, and they were selected by simple random sampling of 2,600 students from the Faculty of Education at Adiyaman University. In this study, the questionnaire "Personal Information Model" was used, which consists of two scales, the first: the alienation of students scale and the scale of attitudes towards the teaching profession, In order to collect data and analyze it using the t-test for independent groups, in order to determine whether the levels of alienation and attitudes towards the teaching profession differ according to the variables of gender and teaching method, While the one-way analysis of the teams was performed to determine if there was any discrimination according to the program type and class variables In order to determine the source of the difference between the groups, Regression analysis was also used in order to determine the level of relationship between levels of organizational behavior and attitudes towards the teaching profession. The results obtained showed that the experienced students had a medium level of alienation. While their attitudes toward the teaching profession were at a high level in the two dimensions, according to gender and class variables, statistically significant differences were seen only at the level of behavior in light of the teaching method variable.

As for the study of Ghobadi and Valadbigi (2012), it aimed to study the elements of functional behavior in a factory in Iran, This study came to clarify the state of job behavior in order to analyze the elements that create job behavior in the factory, By developing a questionnaire that was distributed to a sample of 90 employees. The results of the study indicated that there are fundamental differences in job behavior according to social status in favor of married couples. And found statistically significant differences in job behavior due to the nature of work in favor of non-administrative employees. And in job behavior and employee satisfaction with salaries and wages in favor of higher-paid employees, And in job behavior and the nature of relationships between managers and employees in favor of managers.

8. Summary of previous studies and the location of the current research

Previous studies have benefited from the knowledge of the appropriate methodology and statistical processes, and through which the theoretical framework of the study's subjects and variables was identified. In building the search tool, especially Nazir (2019), Garrido (2021), and Erbas (2014) the current research agrees with previous studies in reviewing the concept of the phenomenon of Phubbing and organizational behavior. The current research is similar to previous studies, especially the study of; Garrido (2021), and Erbas, 2014) in some study variables such as estimation, However, it was distinguished from those studies in its focus on administrators working in vocational education schools, in addition to its focus on variables that were not addressed by previous studies.

9. Methods and Procedures:

To meet the study's goals, the researchers adopted a descriptive survey-based approach

10. Research Population:

The study population consists of all the (650) administrators working in Jordanian vocational education schools.

Table 1: The distribution of the study population

Variable	Category	Frequency	Total
Gender	Male	520	650
	Female	130	
Academic qualification	Postgraduate degree	55	650
	BA degree	345	
	Diploma degree	250	
Years of experience	Five years or less	390	650
	More than five years	260	

11. Research sample

The research sample consisted of a number of administrators working in vocational education schools, and their number is (45) administrative, and table (2) shows the distribution of the research sample according to the research variables.

Table 2: Distribution of the sample according to the research variables

Variable	Category	Frequency	Total
Gender	Male	28	45
	Female	17	
Academic qualification	Postgraduate degree	9	45
	BA degree	25	
	Diploma degree	11	
Years of experience	Five years or less	25	45
	More than five years	20	

12. Research tool

The research tool was developed, with reference to the theoretical literature, and some previous studies such as; Massad study (2016), and Erbas study (2014), In order to achieve the objectives of the research and answer its questions.

The final form of the research tool consisted of (10) paragraphs distributed over two areas: the area of interest in workers, and it consisted of (5) paragraphs, and the assessment field consisted of (5) paragraphs.

To verify the validity of the tool, the validity of the content was approved in terms of the formulation of the paragraphs, and their relevance to the field in which they were placed by presenting those to (8) arbitrators.

To verify the stability of the tool, the internal consistency coefficient was used according to the Cronbach Alpha equation to extract the stability of the study tool by domains, and Table (3) shows the stability coefficients of the tool fields:

Table 3: Cronbach Alpha invariance coefficients for Research tool fields

No.	Area	Cronbach Alpha coefficient value
1.	Provision of attention to employees	0.90
2.	Appreciation	0.89

It is evident from Table (3) that the stability coefficients were acceptable, and to judge the effect of the phenomenon of Phubbing on organizational behavior in vocational schools, the following scale was adopted: low availability (2.33 and less), medium availability (2.34-3.67), and high availability (3.68 and more).

13. Research results and discussion:

Results related to answering the first question, which states: What is the effect of the phenomenon of Phubbing on the organizational behavior of administrators working in vocational schools in the light of two variables; Appreciation, and concern for workers?

To answer this question, the arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the responses of the study sample members in general and for each field of study were calculated, and Table (4) shows this.

Table 4: Means, standard deviations, and rank of the effect of the phenomenon of Phubbing on the organizational behavior of administrators working in vocational schools in the light of the variables of appreciation and concern for workers

No.	Area	Mean	Std.	Rank	Level
1	Provision of attention to employees	3.57	0.89	1	Moderate
2	Appreciation	3.43	1.03	2	Moderate
	Total	3.48	0.92		Moderate

It is noticed from Table (4) that the effect of the phenomenon of Phubbing on the organizational behavior of administrators working in vocational education schools was medium, as the arithmetic mean reached (3.48) and standard deviation (0.92), The domains were medium, and the field of interest in workers came in the first rank, with an arithmetic mean (3.57) and a standard deviation (0.89). In the last rank, the field of estimation came with an arithmetic mean (3.43) and a standard deviation (1.03). As for the paragraphs of each field, the results were as follows:

1. The field of interest in workers: the arithmetic averages, standard deviations, and ranks were calculated for the paragraphs of this field, and Table (5) shows this:

Table 5: Mean, standard deviations, order and degree in the field of employee interest, arranged in descending order

No.	Statement	Mean	Std.	Rank	Level
2	I feel satisfied in light of the privileges available to me	3.52	0.82	1	Moderate
4	I feel safe and secure in my work environment	3.53	1.01	2	Moderate
3	I feel fair where I work	3.57	0.86	3	Moderate
1	I feel satisfied with the possibilities available to me to carry out my administrative duties	3.58	0.92	4	Moderate
5	The school administration is keen to maintain the continuity of the work of the administrators	3.59	1.00	5	Moderate
	Total	3.57	0.90		Moderate

It is noted in Table (5) that the effect of the phenomenon of Phubbing on the organizational behavior of administrators working in vocational education schools in the light of the field of concern to workers was moderate, The arithmetic mean was (3.57) and the standard deviation was (0.90), as the arithmetic means ranged between (3.52 - 3.59), Paragraph (2) came in the first place, which states: "I feel satisfied in light of the privileges available to me." Paragraph (5) came in the last rank, which states: "The school administration is keen on the permanence of the work of the administrators." This may be due to the ability of administrators to join hands despite the presence of social distancing resulting from Phubbing, or they may go through similar circumstances, which did not increase each other's area of interest, This may be attributed to the school administration's ability to provide privileges that simulate the level of ambition of administrators working to raise the standard of living that they hope to reach. This may also be due to the high expectations of administrators that may be commensurate with the

size of the possibilities available in vocational education schools, especially in light of the presence of the phenomenon of Phubbing.

2. Estimation field: The arithmetic averages and standard deviations were calculated for the paragraphs of this field, and Table (6) shows this:

Table 6: Arithmetic means, standard deviations, rank and availability for the estimation field

No.	Statement	Mean	Std.	Rank	Level
3	I feel the presence of moral appreciation in the school	3.35	1.10	1	Moderate
5	I feel the presence of financial motivation in school	3.41	1.06	2	Moderate
2	The school administration considers workload responsibilities when awarding rewards	3.41	1.06	2	Moderate
4	Any achievement I make is instantly rewarded	3.47	1.10	4	Moderate
1	The school administration works to enhance the organizational loyalty of the administrators	3.55	1.05	5	Moderate
	Total	3.43	0.89		Moderate

Table (6) shows that the effect of the phenomenon of Phubbing on the organizational behavior of administrators working in vocational education schools in the field of estimation was Moderate, The arithmetic mean was (3.43) and the standard deviation was (0.89), and all the paragraphs of the field were average. Paragraph (3) came in the first rank, which states: "I feel the presence of moral appreciation in the school." Paragraph (1) came in the last rank, which states: "The school administration works to enhance the organizational loyalty of the administrators." This may be due to the ability of the school administration as well as the working administrators to express their appreciation for the tasks and burdens placed on the administrators themselves. This may also be due to the school administration's belief in the necessity of providing other grading systems. This is in view of the fact that the available assessment systems are insufficient and do not address the human needs of administrators. Such a matter alleviated the impact of the phenomenon of Phubbing, which prevails in the majority of senior administrations of educational institutions.

Results related to the answer to the second question, which states: Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the arithmetic averages of the responses of the study sample members towards the effect of the phenomenon of Phubbing on the organizational behavior of administrators working in vocational schools due to the variables (Gender, years' experience, and educational qualification)?

This question was answered as follows:

a. Gender variable: The arithmetic means and standard deviations were calculated, and the t-test was calculated according to the gender variable, and Table (7) shows that.

Table 7: Arithmetic means, standard deviations, and t-test according to the Gender variable

Area	Gender	Frequency	Mean	Std.	T value	Sig.
Provision of attention to employees	Female	17	3.79	0.74	2.441	0.004**
	Male	28	3.64	0.82		
	Total	45	3.68	0.76		
Appreciation	Female	17	3.57	0.88	0.862	0.016
	Male	28	3.49	0.90		
	Total	45	3.52	0.89		
Total	Female	17	3.68	0.76	1.639	**0.009
	Male	28	3.52	0.89		
	Total	45	3.57	0.80		

** The difference is statistically significant at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$)

To determine whether the differences between the means are statistically significant at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), the t-test was applied. The results in Table (7) indicate that there are statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) according to the gender variable based on the calculated (T) value. It reached (1.639) with a significance level of (0.009), Where the difference was in favor of males, as evidenced by the increase in their arithmetic averages, This may be attributed to the ability of the phenomenon of Phubbing to influence the organizational behavior of males, given that males have the need to secure a safe standard of living capable of maintaining the family level in which they live, They also have the responsibilities of spending and following up on the revenues that enter their homes. On the other hand, we find that males may feel depressed and unable to continue working, especially in light of the phenomenon of Phubbing in their workplace, This is an inevitable result of the direct official's indifference to the administrator's needs and his constant preoccupation with his phone at the expense of taking into account the needs of workers who may feel disappointed if their ongoing needs are ignored, And such a matter has contributed to a significant decrease in the level of their organizational behavior.

B. Years of experience variable: The arithmetic averages and standard deviations were calculated, and the (t-test) test was done according to the years of experience variable, and Table (8) shows that.

Table 8: Arithmetic averages, standard deviations, and t-test according to the variable years of experience

Area	Experience	Frequency	Mean	Std.	T value	Sig.
Provision of attention to employees	Five years or less	25	3.69	0.74	1.673-	0.074
	More than five years	20	3.82	0.83		
	Total	45	3.78	0.78		
Appreciation	Five years or less	25	3.41	0.93	3.428-	0.013**
	More than five years	20	3.64	0.89		
	Total	45	3.53	0.92		
Total	Five years or less	25	3.78	0.78	1.272-	0.202
	More than five year	20	3.53	0.92		
	Total	45	3.64	0.87		

** The difference is statistically significant at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$)

To determine whether the differences between the means are statistically significant at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), the t-test was applied. The results in Table (8) indicate that there are no statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) according to the years of experience variable based on the calculated (T) value, It reached (-1.272) and at a level of significance (0.202), as the difference was in favor of those whose years of experience reached more than five years, as evidenced by the high arithmetic averages. This may be attributed to the prevailing management style, which was characterized by not caring only for its phone and the applications available to it at the expense of providing motives and financial aid and reducing the possibilities that flow into the framework of caring for workers, Which was reflected in the low level of organizational behavior among workers whose years of experience reached more than five years, In addition to the weak interaction between this category of workers; Considering that their tasks intersect with each other, Which led to more complexity in interacting and synergizing with each other on the one hand, And with the school administration on the other hand, and thus the weakness of the school administration's ability to deal with the difficulties and obstacles faced by the workers, Providing more attention to their affairs, providing a great deal of potential, and working on their development, development, and motivation, Rewarding their efforts and raising their standard of living.

c. Educational qualification variable: Arithmetic averages and standard deviations were calculated according to the educational qualification variable, and Table (9) shows that:

Table 9: Arithmetic averages and standard deviations according to the educational qualification variable

Area academic qualification	Category	Frequency	Mean	Std.
Provision of attention to employees	Postgraduate degree	9	3.79	0.55
	BA degree	25	3.88	0.82
	Diploma degree	11	3.76	0.79
	Total	45	3.76	0.76
Appreciation	Postgraduate degree	9	3.54	0.85
	BA degree	25	3.68	0.86
	Diploma degree	11	3.59	0.90
	Total	45	3.73	0.87
Total	Postgraduate degree	9	3.58	1.61
	BA degree	25	3.67	1.70
	Diploma degree	11	3.52	1.62
	Total	45	3.58	1.48

It is noticed from Table (9) that there are apparent differences between the arithmetic averages, according to the educational qualification variable, Those in the (Bachelor's) category got the highest arithmetic average of (3.67), and those in the (Postgraduate) category ranked second with an average of 3.58. And in the last rank came from those in the (diploma) category, as the arithmetic average reached (3.52), To determine whether the differences between the averages are statistically significant at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), the One Way ANOVA has been applied, and the results of the analysis of variance are as shown in Table (10).

Table 10: Scheffe test for dimensional differences due to educational qualification variable

Academic qualification	Mean	Postgraduate degree	BA degree	Diploma degree
		3.59	3.68	3.52
Postgraduate degree	3.59	-	0.952	0.934
BA degree	3.68	0.952	-	0.387
Diploma degree	3.52	0.934	0.387	-

The difference is statistically significant at the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$)

It appears from Table (10) that the difference came: in favor of the category of administrators who are in the category (bachelor) when compared with administrators who are in the category (diploma).

14. Recommendations

After reviewing the results of the study, the researchers recommend the following:

1. The need to pay attention to the development of a set of practices and behaviors prevalent among workers in vocational education departments through deepening appreciation and developing its aspects and taking care of workers in a way that leads their organizational behavior in an effective manner.

2. Conducting more studies on the impact of the phenomenon of Phubbing on the various organizational aspects in educational institutions of all kinds and the state of organizational alienation it caused, and maintaining a close social distance between the administrations of vocational education schools and administrators on the one hand, and the administrators themselves on the other.

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